

Urban Wetland Methane Emissions in the Greater Toronto Area: Chamber-Based Scaling and Comparison with FLAME-GTA

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Introduction

Methane flux measurements from representative urban wetlands in the Greater Toronto Area (GTA) were used to characterize spatial variability and generate regional emission estimates for swamp (forested wetlands with woody vegetation) and marsh (herbaceous emergent wetland) systems consistent with Facility Level and Area Methane Emissions inventory for the Greater Toronto Area (FLAME-GTA) (Mostafavi Pak et al. 2021).

Methodology

Regional methane emissions from wetlands were estimated using a bottom-up scaling approach based on site-level floating-chamber measurements and wetland area statistics from the FLAME-GTA (Mostafavi Pak et al. 2021). Methane flux measurements were obtained across a range of aquatic and wetland environments within the GTA; however, regional scaling and inventory comparison were restricted to wetland classes with direct classification correspondence between datasets, namely swamp and marsh wetlands.

Mean methane flux for swamp wetlands was calculated from measurements collected within the Pottageville Swamp Conservation Area across contrasting microtopographic substrates characterized by organic debris accumulation and rocky bottom conditions. Marsh wetland fluxes were derived from measurements conducted at Evergreen Brickworks and Downsview Park marsh systems. For each wetland class, mean methane flux was computed as the arithmetic mean of site-level total fluxes, where total flux represents the sum of diffusive methane exchange and equivalent ebullitive flux derived from observed bubble-release frequency and event magnitude. To facilitate comparison with regional inventory approaches and account for measurement seasonality, class-specific mean methane fluxes ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) were converted to growing-season areal emissions (kg km^{-2} per 165-day growing season period) consistent with FLAME-GTA wetland seasonality assumptions. Regional emissions were subsequently estimated by multiplying class-specific area emissions by mapped wetland area. Swamp scaling employed inundated wetland-edge area (30.52 km^2) derived from National Wetland Inventory polygons buffered inward by 3 m to approximate shallow-water zones consistent with floating-chamber deployment conditions, while marsh scaling used FLAME-GTA marsh area estimates (94 km^2). Inventory-based methane emissions for comparison were calculated using FLAME-GTA wetland emission factors and reported wetland areas.

Results

Mean methane flux across swamp sites was $6.46 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, equivalent to $1,472 \text{ kg km}^{-2}$ per 165-day growing season, while marsh wetlands exhibited substantially lower mean fluxes of $0.19 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, corresponding to 43 kg km^{-2} per 165-day period. Applying measurement-consistent spatial scaling yielded

regional methane emissions of approximately **44.9 kt** per growing season for swamp wetlands (30.52 km² inundated edge area) and **4.1 kt** per growing season for marsh wetlands (94 km²). In contrast, application of FLAME-GTA emission factors produced lower estimates of 2.4 kt yr⁻¹ for swamp wetlands and 0.71 kt yr⁻¹ for marsh wetlands. Despite differences in magnitude, both approaches consistently identified swamp wetlands as the dominant contributor to regional wetland methane emissions within the GTA. The observed discrepancy likely reflects methodological contrasts between chamber-based observations capable of capturing localized emission hotspots and episodic ebullition, and inventory emission factors representing spatially averaged conditions. The use of measurement-consistent inundated-area scaling further highlights the sensitivity of regional methane estimates to assumptions regarding hydrologically active wetland extent.

Fig. 1. Mean (\pm SE) methane flux across sampled GTA wetlands. Bars show total flux (diffusive + ebullitive) and error bars represent standard error (SE). Wetlands are displayed in two panels to distinguish high- and low-emission systems.

References

Mostafavi Pak N, Heerah S, Zhang J, et al (2021) The Facility Level and Area Methane Emissions inventory for the Greater Toronto Area (FLAME-GTA). *Atmos Environ* 252:118319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2021.118319>